

TEACHERS' VIEWS ON ACADEMIC WRITING ASSIGNMENTS GENERATED BY ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE: HOW DO THEY AFFECT THE TEACHING METHODS IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract. *Generative artificial intelligence technologies in higher education have rapidly influenced academic writing, raising concerns about academic and linguistic integrity. This transformation in foreign language teaching creates a critical conflict between the effectiveness of technology and the ability of students to learn through real means. To answer this new question, this study examines the attitude of teachers of “Academic Writing” and “English for Academic Purposes” at two Kazakhstani universities towards tasks generated by artificial intelligence, with an emphasis on pedagogical responses and linguistic integrity. In the course of the study, conducted using mixed methods, 15 teachers were interviewed. Descriptive statistics were used to identify the validity, evaluation, and institutional support of quantitative data. The transcripts of the interviews were examined during the thematic analysis. The results show that most teachers have worked with AI-generated assignments that are well-written grammatically but lack creativity, critical thinking, or student voice. Excessive use of AI also worries teachers about critical thinking and reflective learning in students. Teachers use multimodal assessments, oral defenses, reflective comments, and drafts to emphasize the importance of the learning process rather than the results. The study highlights the lack of institutional norms regarding artificial intelligence in assignments and shows how foreign language teachers combine technological innovation and academic integrity.*

Key words: *academic writing; artificial intelligence; English for academic purposes; teaching strategies; higher education.*

Introduction

Artificial intelligence is rapidly becoming a reality and transforming existing schools. Generative artificial intelligence techniques such as ChatGPT and other mass language models quickly create coherent and natural-sounding writing, making it difficult to distinguish between human-generated and machine-generated content [Yan D., 2023]. In this regard, students are increasingly using these technologies to speed up writing assignments, creating new opportunities for accessibility and efficiency. Along with increasing efficiency, artificial intelligence is being introduced into educational processes to improve language and writing acquisition. Some scholars [Singh M., 2023] argue that generative AI technologies can automate composition, increase linguistic accuracy, and help students in academic speech. Popular writing programs such as Grammarly demonstrate how artificial intelligence is already being used in academic writing by checking grammar, style, and language with minimal human intervention [Singh M., 2023]. When properly integrated into the learning process, these tools can improve students' language awareness and writing skills.

Although generative AI has many advantages, it raises concerns about academic integrity and authorship. Teachers are concerned that students are using AI to complete assignments. Although this provides original content, it may not reflect the student's intellectual engagement [Yan D., 2023]. The content created with the help of artificial intelligence violates the rules of academic authorship and intellectual property, but at the same time avoids detection of plagiarism, since it is "new" and not copied. Recent research suggests updating evaluation methods, improving institutional policies, and introducing process-oriented approaches to evaluation. These strategies should make appropriate use of technology while remaining innovative and intellectually honest [Singh M., 2023]. Teachers fear that students may end up relying more on language and ideas created by artificial intelligence than on constant writing practice, intellectual struggle, and critical evaluation. These problems are compounded by gaps in the management of higher education. The regulatory framework in the field of AI is still evolving, and institutions often lack ethical principles in the field of AI [Jared B., Hanna K., 2024].

The impact of AI on universities and academic degrees is being studied more and more. Some scientists [Selwyn N., 2024] reports that educational institutions are adopting AI technologies, but they must be careful not to undermine academic standards. There are scholars who agrees [Luckin R., 2025] praising AI for improving learning, but warning that unregulated use could harm creativity and intellectual property rights. According to UNESCO [UNESCO, 2024] report, international policy discussions highlight the transformative importance of AI in education, highlighting its potential benefits and ethical challenges. Research in technology-based learning focuses on digital learning systems or technological infrastructures, rather than how teachers adapt to learning environments mediated by artificial intelligence [Kaur et al., 2022]. There is a lack of empirical research in the evidence-based educational literature on how technological progress affects teachers' assessment methods, daily routines, and classroom decision-making [Barrasso A., Spilios K., 2021]. As artificial intelligence is rapidly spreading in higher education, teachers are enthusiastic about technological innovation, but concerned about academic integrity and control of learning, which increases uncertainty in this area [Butakor P., 2023]. In such situations, it is important to consider the teacher's reaction to artificial intelligence, not just student behavior or technology.

This study examines how teachers at two Kazakhstani universities combine the use of artificial intelligence and loyalty to themselves as specialists in language and academic knowledge to fill these gaps. The study examines how teachers adapt their teaching and grading methods to tasks created using artificial intelligence. Examples include oral defense, reflexive remarks, and drafts [Butakor P., 2023]. This study complements discussions about artificial intelligence in higher education by focusing on the real-life experiences of professors and pedagogical reactions that are often ignored. In light of the growing academic dishonesty in universities, this study examines how professors handle assignments created with artificial intelligence and how they teach students about linguistic honesty.

Finally, our research contributes to the discussion of how artificial intelligence can improve academic writing and English language programs. The study sheds light on how foreign language teachers strive to maintain intellectual engagement, critical thinking and an authentic student voice by introducing technological innovations

through an analysis of teachers' views and adaptation methods. These results can form the basis for teaching systems focused on artificial intelligence and general discussions in the field of English language teaching regarding written classes, test development and academic integrity in the digital age.

Main part

In this part we will discuss the methods and results we got during the research. The research uses qualitative and quantitative methods. The combination of these methods makes it possible to fully explore the problems of AI in universities. Qualitative semi-structured interviews focus on professors' reactions to the impact of artificial intelligence on academic work, while a quantitative survey provides a broad overview.

The sample includes English language teachers who specialize in “Academic Writing”, as well as in “English for Academic Purposes” and evaluate students' written work. These teachers were chosen because they most often encounter students working with artificial intelligence during the learning process, which includes evaluating written assignments. A targeted sample was conducted to ensure that the participants had experience writing texts using artificial intelligence. At the survey stage, 15 teachers who met these requirements were interviewed. After that, 8 professors were selected for semi-structured interviews based on a targeted selection based on criteria. Their choice was based on their willingness to share their experience of completing tasks generated by artificial intelligence and their responses to survey questions. The two-stage sampling method used in the study allowed us to obtain a broad understanding of the opinions of scientists and more accurate qualitative data on their pedagogical reactions.

The data was collected using structured questionnaires and semi-structured interviews. The questionnaire was compiled using academic honesty, writing using artificial intelligence and AI in the classroom. The study included closed-ended questions about teachers' views on the use of artificial intelligence in educational projects, and open-ended questions about their experiences and concerns about students' linguistic integrity. Two experts in educational technology and English language teaching checked the questionnaire for clarity and reliability of the content before distribution. Semi-structured interviews were conducted with 8 teachers to better understand their experiences. In the interview guide, the teachers discussed academic papers created using artificial intelligence. Participants gave informed consent before each 25-30 minute interview, which was recorded on audio and transcribed for analysis. The interviews were analyzed using the techniques of Brown and Clarke [Brown V., Clarke V., 2006] to familiarize themselves with the data, encode it, create a topic, and interpret it. Combining quantitative and qualitative data allowed for triangulation, which reinforced the conclusions. The participants agreed on the purpose of the study after they were informed. Quantitative survey responses were analyzed using percentages and frequencies to determine the use of artificial intelligence and faculty opinions. Qualitative interview data was processed using thematic analysis, starting with "authenticity" and "pedagogical strategies". We compared these codes with the survey results and distributed them by topic to ensure consistency using the thematic analysis of Brown and Clarke [Braun V., Clarke V., 2006].

This study shows how teachers at two Kazakhstani universities understand and solve the problems associated with assigning AI to students. Interviews and surveys revealed issues of authenticity and honesty, pedagogical innovations, institutional needs, and AI identification experiences. These principles are then illustrated with analysis and

excerpts. According to this study, teachers should balance the legitimacy of the course with technological adaptation. Artificial intelligence in the classroom has enormous potential to improve education, but concerns remain about its impact on children's memory and language use. Oral defenses, reflective comments, and mandatory drafts help teachers solve these problems by focusing on the process rather than the result, and encouraging student participation in learning. Teachers and students need a framework to explain artificial intelligence (AI) and its inconsistent use in different classrooms. The emotional aspects associated with the use of AI should warn us against technology replacing human elements in higher education. Based on these findings, universities should integrate artificial intelligence into their teaching methods without compromising students' honesty, decency, and critical thinking. The specific results of the study were revealed regarding how often artificial intelligence is used in student work. According to the data obtained, tasks created with the help of artificial intelligence prevail in students' academic writing. According to the survey results, most of the teachers completed tasks related to AI. Table 1 shows that 60% of participants encounter AI-generated tasks from time to time, and 20% often. Also, 20% said they rarely encounter it. These data indicate that writing using artificial intelligence is currently becoming more widespread in the learning process of students (see table 1).

Table 1. Frequency of occurrence of works created with the help of artificial intelligence

Frequency of occurrence of works created with the help of artificial intelligence	Respondents %
Sometimes	60%
Often	20%
Rarely	20%

In the course of the study, the participating teacher found a gap between the mastery of concepts and the fluency of the text. This suggests that the information generated by AI may seem excellent from an academic point of view, but the level of student engagement in the subject may be minimal.

"In the essay, we see advanced academic work, but the student could not provide an adequate justification for the organization of argumentation during the discussion in the lesson" (Participant 3).

The teachers also noted that the text generated by AI lacks personality. One of the respondents said:

"As a rule, there is something special in the work of students. Sometimes they are sincere, despite the flaws. Artificial intelligence creates polished, empty prose" (Participant 5).

One respondent also added:

"Sometimes, essays are written in a very similar style, although students usually have completely different writing abilities" (Participant 6).

These trends show that written language created with the help of artificial intelligence can reduce the diversity of student utterances and standardize language

expressions. The results also show that teachers are adjusting their teaching methods as artificial intelligence helps them solve more tasks.

One of the teachers explained how the step-by-step submission of papers helps them track student progress.:

“To prepare for the final essay, students submit a summary and a draft version. Then you can understand how their thinking has changed and what they wanted to convey.”

These changes in the teaching methodology imply a focus on the assessment process. Nowadays, scientists pay special attention to the entire writing process, not just the final product.

The results show that the issues of language purity are one of the most serious problems faced by students using artificial intelligence in their homework. Teachers recognize the ability of writing to create well-structured and grammatically literate text using artificial intelligence. They emphasized that complex language is important, but it does not always indicate intellectual engagement. The most notable result of the survey was that most scientists believe that writing tasks created using artificial intelligence reduce cognitive processes associated with academic writing, including creativity, reflection, and critical thinking. Table 2 shows that 47% of respondents believe that artificial intelligence improves speech quality, but 40% also believe that it hinders originality and critical thinking. The impact of artificial intelligence on students' written language is worrisome, as only 13% of respondents noted no significant impact.

Table 2. Perception of the influence of AI on linguistic integrity

Perception of the influence of AI on linguistic integrity	Respondents %
Endangers critical thinking and originality	47%
Improves linguistic quality, but lacks authenticity	40%
Lack of significant impact	13%

The results also demonstrate the importance of teaching tactics that make the learning process obvious. The results obtained indicate that artificial intelligence is a technological and pedagogical problem. We need additional ways to check the cognitive activity of students if we cannot determine whether their written speech is authentic by looking at the final result. These methods may include meaningful criticism, oral explanations of written arguments, and step-by-step presentation of written papers.

Teachers use a number of pedagogical methods to solve the problem of increasing the number of homework created using artificial intelligence. Many teachers have rejected written answers in order to make the learning process more transparent. The survey showed that process-oriented methods are increasingly being used to test students' performance and engage them in their studies. Table 3 shows that 60% of the teachers wanted students to provide drafts with comments.

Table 3. Implemented pedagogical strategies

Implemented pedagogical strategies	Respondents %
Drafts and meaningful comments	47%
Oral defense	33%
Multimodal tasks	20%

The interview data suggest that comments and drafts are used to track students' intellectual development while writing texts. The professors say that this method shows how ideas develop from drafts to finished works. Drafts clarify the students' thought processes, one of the participants said. "I see how my students' thinking develops through drafts and reflections"

This example shows that draft-based assessment is crucial for education.

Along with these strategies, several faculty members have proposed multimodal assignments to increase student engagement. In these projects, students must explain their ideas using video presentations, podcasts, and digital storytelling.

One respondent replied, "I asked the class to make video presentations on the topics of their essays. The presentation shows whether they understand their ideas." (Participant 2)

Apparently, multimodal assessment complicates academic work and does not allow automated systems to replace interaction with students. They also teach digital communication, argumentation, and audience interaction.

These pedagogical innovations are part of a broader trend in process-oriented learning and assessment. Teachers evaluate students for developing a concept, organization, and presentation, not for the finished work. This strategy helps teachers track students' intellectual growth, rather than just evaluating their written work. Thus, teachers are actively reviewing their teaching methods in response to the challenges of artificial intelligence, rather than simply responding to them.

Effective academic writing requires grammatical precision, posture, engagement, and authorial positioning in accordance with discursive and meta-discursive approaches [Zhao J., Liu Y., 2021]. The absence of these elements in the texts generated by artificial intelligence suggests that linguistic form alone is not enough to determine communicative competence. Thus, these results enhance previous theories by showing how AI can standardize speech by weakening the dialogical and interpersonal aspects of academic writing. It also shows how AI-mediated writing can obscure the cognitive processes underlying the formation of statements, evaluation of evidence, and substantiation of grounds, contributing to argumentation theory. Students should clearly substantiate scientifically based statements in academic writing, especially in the form of argumentation [Abdelrahim A., Abdelrahim M., 2019]. The results show that students can copy the forms of argumentation generated by artificial intelligence systems without understanding their reasoning.

This shows that active cognitive activity is still needed to improve reasoning skills, not just reading well-structured texts. Since critical views on educational technologies [Selwyn N., 2024] emphasize that digital tools should enhance human cognitive abilities rather than replace them, the findings have great theoretical significance. This study

confirms both points of view, showing that cognitive substitution and identity bias are dangerous. In language education, writing helps students develop their own voice. AI-written texts lack personality, which calls into question the potential of technology to create their own character and puts forward arguments in favor of AI that go beyond computing, in favor of language and authorship.

Another key discovery is new learning strategies that focus on student achievement. Teachers of this course often use multimodal assignments, oral defenses or presentations, reflective comments, step-by-step drafting with feedback, and other process-oriented methods. These strategies emphasize intellectual improvement over time [Abramova et al., 2024]. These methods are based on learning-oriented assessment principles that consider assessment as a process (iterative, dialogical, progressive) rather than as a final judgment. Teachers should instruct students to write drafts and reflective notes to document their reflections and develop self-regulation and metacognition. Reflexive learning strategies in higher education institutions often lead to such results [Mahlangu T., 2024]. Oral defense is another effective way to prove ownership of intellectual property. Students' oral defense of their written assignments can show whether they understand them conceptually.

Future research should determine whether these learning strategies promote critical thinking, writing, and intellectual property among students in diverse academic environments. The research is unique because professors are leading educational transformations in response to the challenges posed by artificial intelligence. Instead of relying solely on institutional constraints, teachers are revising assessment processes to enhance the credibility of learning.

Conclusion

The study showed that the rapid introduction of generative artificial intelligence into the higher education system is most changing the practice of academic writing in language schools, where linguistic integrity and genuine intellectual engagement are key learning objectives. According to the results of previous studies, teachers found the term papers created with the help of artificial intelligence to be well-written, but devoid of creativity, individuality and critical thinking. There is an obvious growing contradiction between technical efficiency and real-world learning. Teachers use oral defenses, multimodal assessments, reflective commentary, and step-by-step drafting to address students' learning paths and academic integrity. The study also revealed a key flaw in the existing system: the lack of common standards for evaluating and teaching artificial intelligence in the classroom. This study analyzes the life experiences of teachers in English language teaching using artificial intelligence in order to provide an empirical understanding of pedagogical adaptation in the classroom, rather than relying solely on institutional regulation. Such research makes it possible to create more complex learning systems that use artificial intelligence without compromising language or critical thinking. Due to the small sample size and the presence of two institutions, the results may not be applicable elsewhere. Therefore, future research should examine how students perceive written language using artificial intelligence, how artificial intelligence will affect the development of academic literacy, and how well process-oriented assessments work in various institutional and disciplinary settings. Comparative and longitudinal studies are needed to understand how educational institutions can adapt to learning using artificial intelligence, at the same time allowing students to engage in significant intellectual pursuits.

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